

BIOCHEMICAL BASIS OF CANCER IMMUNOTHERAPY. RECEPTORS AND SIGNALLING PATHWAYS TARGETED BY IMMUNOTHERAPEUTIC PREPARATIONS.**Lupu A.,***student, Faculty of General Medicine, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu" Chisinau, Republic of Moldova***Simionica Eugeniu***PhD, university lector, State University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Nicolae Testemitanu" Chisinau, Republic of Moldova***Abstract**

Tumor cells can inhibit immune responses against their survival by activating inhibitory immune checkpoint proteins, which are PD-1 (programmed death receptor) CTLA-4 (cytotoxic T-lymphocyte antigen). PD-1 is the membrane receptor responsible for signal transduction into intracellular compartments and has two ligands PD-L1 and PD-L2. The effect of PD-1/PD-L1 complex is to inhibit the function and proliferation of T cells, resulting in the activation of T cell apoptosis. CTLA-4 has the structure of a type 1 transmembrane glycoprotein and has two ligands, CD80 and CD86, which are found on T regulatory and antigen-presenting cells. Endocytosis of the CTLA-4/CD80 complex results in the T-lymphocyte remaining in a state of low co-stimulation with maintenance of a suppressed counter tumor response. The main immunotherapeutic agents are monoclonal antibodies targeting CTLA-4, PD-1 receptors and PD-L1 and PD-L2 ligands.

Keywords: cancer, immunotherapy, PD-1, PD-L1, CTLA-4, structure, signalling pathways, monoclonal antibodies.

Cancer is defined as a rapid growth of abnormal cells in any part of the human body that can invade adjacent tissues and spread to other organs via the lymphatic or blood pathway. After many years of research into the biochemistry, clinical aspects and treatment of cancer, scientists have focused on the hardest aspect of fighting cancer - immunity. Tumor cells can suppress immune responses directed against their survival by activating immune checkpoint inhibitory proteins, which are PD-1 and CTLA-4. Blocking these proteins makes it impossible to suppress anti-tumor immunity and thus restores normal T-lymphocyte function. The signaling pathways of these receptors contain key structures that can be targeted by immunotherapeutic preparations. These structures are present as the interaction between the receptors and their ligands. CTLA-4 is the first receptor to be discovered, the ligands of which are CD80 and CD86 receptors. Another complex is represented by PD-1 and two ligands PD-L1 and PD-L2. The complexes listed are the targets of current immunotherapeutic treatment. [1][2]

PD-1, which is considered the most commonly used receptor in the fight against cancer. It is a transmembrane glycoprotein and contains 288 amino acids. The domain of this receptor, which is located on the

surface of the T-cell, is the primary domain, whose role is to interact with PD-L1 on the surface of the antigen-presenting cell. The intracytoplasmic domain contains two tyrosine-based signalling sites: a tyrosine-based inhibitory site (ITIM) and a tyrosine immunoreceptor switch site (ITSM). The PD-1/PD-L1 pathway itself comprises several signalling steps which for the T cell can be 'positive' and 'negative'. The first 'trigger' signal is the interaction of the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) with the TCR. The second trigger signal is presented by the formation of the CD80/CD28 complex. The third signal is the inhibitory one and comprises in itself two simultaneous interactions: PD-1/PD-L1 and CD80/CTLA-4. The T cell with the help of these signals regulates its activity and depending on the prevalence of one or the other type of signal can be subsequently activated or, conversely, inhibited and destroyed. The PD-1/PD-L1 complex produces a very strong counteraction to the MHC/TCR signal, i.e. the 'positive' signal. At the same time, this complex stops ZAP70 phosphorylation, inhibits PI3K and PTEN activity. As a result, the glycolysis process switches to beta-oxidation due to inhibition of the PI3K-AKT and ZAP70-ERK pathways and, as a result, the T cell is destroyed by apoptosis. [3][4][5]

Figure 1. Activation effects of PD-L1

CTLA-4 likewise has the structure of a transmembrane glycoprotein and consists of 233 amino acids. This immune checkpoint consists of 4 domains: the leader, the binding domain, the transmembrane region and the cytoplasmic tail. The intracytoplasmic tail of CTLA-4 exhibits two phosphorylation motifs by the enzymes FYN (proto-oncogene tyrosine kinase), LYN (tyrosine protein kinase) and LCK (lymphocyte-specific protein tyrosine kinase). In addition, the tyrosine at position 201 of CTLA-4 interacts with LRBA, which prevents its early lysosomal degradation. Signalling of the CTLA-4/CD80 pathway starts primarily from the expression of CTLA-4 on the T cell surface. This process is influenced by a multitude of factors at the membrane, cytoplasmic and nuclear or genetic level. At the nuclear level NFAT, Foxp3, STAT1, Fos, MYC and Bcl-2 bind to the CTLA-4 gene promoter. At the cytoplasmic level AP-1 and AP-2 bind to the GVVVKM and YVKM gene sections for the purpose of maintaining stable levels of CTLA-4. MicroRNAs miR-155, miR-224-5p, miR-324-5p, miR-488-5p, miR-302a are involved in CTLA-4 gene transcription and its performance at the endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi apparatus. After release at the T cell surface CTLA-4 interferes with TCR and forms a complex of CTLA-4, TRIM, LAX and Rab8. After interaction with ligands or in the absence of the need for representation on the cell surface, CTLA-4 is destroyed at the endocytosomal level. This process begins primarily with the loss of LRBA protein at the cytoplasmic tail. Subsequently,

endosome formation requires the involvement of clathrin, dynamin and AP 2 protein, which binds to the CTLA-4 tail in place of LRBA. After internalization CTLA-4 can be lysosomally distributed or re-incorporated on the membrane surface of the T cell. The functional effect of CTLA-4 interaction on T reg lymphocyte is that CD80 on the CPA surface has much higher affinity for CTLA-4 on the T reg surface than for CD28 on the conventional T lymphocyte. The tumour micro-environment differs from the usual immune cell environment by the abundant amount of regulatory T cells, which in turn cause the attachment of CD80 or CD86 receptors only to CTLA-4 receptors and the result of this difference is low co-stimulation of conventional T cells with preservation of the inhibited anticancer response. If it is possible to block CTLA-4 by antibodies, CD80 or CD86 have only one attachment site - CD28 (fig 2). This blockade can be performed by different methods, as for example direct receptor blockade on T reg or on the constant fragment (Fc) that is attached to the macrophage. The result is one - depletion of Treg, formation of CD80 or CD86 complex with CD27, increased co-stimulation of conventional T cells and adequate immune response. Subsequent internalization of the CTLA-4/CD80 complex leads to decreased co-stimulation of conventional T cells with subsequent formation of the ineffective immune response.[7][6][9][12]

Figure 2. CTLA-4 functions [9]

So, at present FDA has approved 3 immunotherapeutic preparations, which are anti-PD-L1 monoclonal antibodies, and these are Atezolizumab, Durvalumab and Avelumab. These preparations are IgG class PD-L1 blockers, which are formed from Fab and Fc, where on the VL surface of Fab there are 6 loops: HCDR1, HCDR2, HCDR3, LCDR3, LCDR1, LCDR2. The structural difference of these preparations is that different IgG loops are involved in the binding process with the immune checkpoint receptor. The affinity of certain loops towards the receptor or ligand does not lead to irreversible transformation of the structure, but only blocks the binding site. In 2022 and 2023 the FDA approved two new preparations, nivolumab and pembrolizumab, which are monoclonal antibodies of PD-1. The blockers of this receptor are of the IgG4 class in which the constant region is identical, but the variable region in pembrolizumab involves the C'D and C,C' loops and nivolumab only the C'D site. The monoclonal antibody to CTLA-4 ipilimumab is not yet FDA approved and is in the investigational process. Ipilimumab is assigned to the n IgG class, in which its constant region has the ability to induce antibody-mediated cytotoxicity. [8][10][11]

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